
Project: *Global Baroque: transcultural and transhistorical approaches to Latin America*

THE BIG CITY AROUND THE OLD CHURCH

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History

The Church of San Francisco is located at Madero Street and is all that remains of the church and monastery complex.

This complex was the headquarter of the first twelve Franciscan monks headed by Martín de Valencia who came to Mexico to evangelize in New Spain.

It was the headquarter of the Franciscans and was built over Montezuma II's zoo.

The monastery was a big building with 32,224 square meters, and after the Reform War, part of the monastery was demolished. Once to demolish buildings were expensive the city kept some like the *De Profundus Room*, where now resides a bakery; and at the corners of Venustiano Carranza and Eje Central the Old Chapels of San Antonio and Calvario still remains.

The church standing today is the third construction built; the first two sunk into the soft soil. This last one was built between 1710 and 1716.

Although the entire building is known as the Francisco Church, the entrance at Madero St. is the entrance to the Balvanera Chapel.

The church main façade, dating from 1710 is walled and cannot be seen.

The chapel's statues were removed, but decorative elements such as volutes, sculpted leaves and flowers and the estipite (inverted truncated pyramid) columns with medallions.

Inside there is an 18th century altarpiece dedicated to Virgin of Guadalupe.

In the main church, there is a large gilded main altar that is the one that replace the original Baroque one, that has been reconstructed because Neoclassic artist Jeronimo Antonio Gil left a drawing of it.

The cloister is inside the Methodist church, the floors had been preserved, and also the walls in the *De Profundus Room*, is also original.

The San Francisco Convent

When we stand before an old building, in special a church inside a very religious society, and this old building brings the history of this city, the first thought is that is a monument and we must keep it as the testimony of the city's history.

The San Francisco church represents the Mexico City's history but it doesn't keep the same appearance of the Franciscan monks building, of the colonial time, of about half century before.

The first problem was that this church is in the Mexico City's downtown, one of the largest city in the world, and had occupied 32,224 square meters before. In the original configuration, this church was the Franciscan Order headquarter and afterwards has witnessed important events. The place was the first school of art in Mexico at the colonial time, where youth natives learned religion with the monks, they taught their art and culture as a political matter: the Hermán Cortés funeral; also granted the refugees of the Count Garve's rebellion; and the celebration of the end of the Mexican War of Independence¹.

After the Reform War, the monastery of San Francisco was demolished and divided in many properties of the government to give place to new roads. Parts of those old buildings are now the Methodist's church and the Panadería Ideal bakery.²

The present entrance is the Balvanera Chapel; the church was rebuilt three times due to sunk "at the soft soil underneath Mexico city"³. The entrance has a well-crafted façade done by Lorenzo Rodríguez (1704-1774) that also done the Metropolitan Tabernacle. There is a 18th century altarpiece dedicated to the Virgin of Guadalupe and the Second Station of the Station of the Cross also.⁴

There is an original paint of the neoclassical artist Jeronimo Antonio Gil (1732 – 1789), so the main altar was reconstructed and has replaced the original Baroque one. Inside the bakery there is an original wall of the *De Profundis Room* still in opposition with the rest that was remodeled to attend the bakery. The old cloister, on the Glance Street, belongs nowadays to the Methodist Church and the floor was preserved as the original.⁵

About the building's materiality, it is important the use of the *tezontle* that is a porous reddish volcanic stone, that allowed the Mexican architects to build "their church façades subtle textures and rich colors that were unique in the word"⁶. The Mexican art also provide the world with a new material that change the European Art materiality with the carmine pigment.

The carmine is an organic pigment made of animal (female insect), the use of denomination "carmine" in Europe belong to the middle of the XVIII century, and the recipe to the production has been

¹ GALINDO; GALINDO,2002, pp. 128-130.

² HUMPREY, Chris, 2005, pp 35-36..

³ Idem.

⁴ GALINDO; GALINDO, 2002, pp. 128-130

⁵ GALINDO; GALINDO, 2002, pp. 128-130

⁶ BAILEY, 2005, p.9

published since 1656.⁷ Before, the red pigment in Europa was a vegetable based one, the lacquer of *garança*, made of the root of the *garança* plant. The pigment that comes from this carbon base is not stable and needs a process called *lacquer* to become a stable pigment; the *lacquer* process makes it insoluble⁸.

The introduction of this carmine brought an innovation to the European art production, but unfortunately some artists didn't know that the new beautiful red wasn't a stable pigment and in the contact with the air and light has a fast oxidation, so the ink fade out quickly.

An important pigment at colonial time, the ultramarine blue, natural pigment done by the *lápiz lazúli* stone, was a pigment done by crushing the stone, it was a very hard process, separating all the gray parts and leaving only the pure intense blue. To make this pigment, the stones from Afghanistan were used and after the contact with the Latin America; the stones came from Chile also⁹.

The red stone used as a constructive resource that is possible to see in the right of the principal façade of the Balvanera Chapel, is the *tezontle*, this was a distinctive material used in civil and religious construction (Metropolitan Cathedral of Mexico). The Latin American materials influenced the European art production after different materials were carried to there.

References

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⁷ MAYER, 1999, 35-49

⁸ SMITH, 2008, p. 12

⁹ MAYER, 1999, p. 54-55.